

Journalists' Awareness and Knowledge of Social Media Applications for Investigation in Nigeria

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Abstract:

This paper examined the level of awareness of investigative journalists on the benefits of Social Media Applications (SMAs) for sourcing information in the Southwest of Nigeria; ascertained investigative journalists' knowledge of SMAs functions and usage for investigative purposes and found out whether investigative journalists employ SMAs for investigative reasons. Survey method was adopted with a sample of 344 investigative journalists. The multi-stage sampling technique was used for the administration of copies of questionnaire. Descriptive statistics of simple percentage and frequency count was employed for the data analysis. Findings indicated that investigative journalists had a high level of awareness of the benefits of SMAs for gathering investigative data and also displayed a high knowledge of the functions and usage of SMAs for investigation but are significantly challenged by non-conformity of SMAs to their organizations' workflow and policy combined with the ethical dilemma inherent in social media application for investigation. The study concluded that the awareness and knowledge of SMAs resulted in minimal usage by investigative journalists. Hence, this study recommended that media organisations should ameliorate challenges of investigative journalists utilizing SMAs for investigation by providing facilities that could improve their usage. Journalists should be devoted to the exploration of social media technology and engage ethically in the use of the diverse SMAs for investigative purposes.

Keywords: Investigative journalist, awareness, knowledge, social media applications, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Social media, as described by Kaplan and Haenlein (2012), is a collection of internet-based programs that builds on the conceptual and technical underpinnings of web 2.0 and permits the production and exchange of user-generated content. Social media platforms have been broadly embraced as a tool for communication across industries, regions, cultures, and demographics. Social media is used frequently for communication, and people are increasingly using it to find news (Barthel, Shearer, Goettfried, & Mitchell, 2015). The trend of people going to social media for news is partially a result of the comfort and familiarity that social media usage has brought about, but it is also a result of how quickly information can be shared through social media channels. Since social media is an essential instrument for exchanging information in real time, it has developed into a key hub for the discovery of breaking news and attracted a large audience of journalists.

Over the past few years, social media platforms, particularly X, have been widely used in newsrooms and have become an essential tool for journalists. Journalists use this toolset in a variety of ways, like monitoring social media for breaking news and relevant information, using it to locate sources and eyewitnesses, and taking advantage of its wide audience to crowdsource various viewpoints on noteworthy events. Social media has an abundance of information that is unprecedented in terms of volume, variety, and velocity. This abundance of information is changing how professional journalists gather and transmit news.

According to Broersma and Graham (2012), social networks are a huge pool of collective intelligence that enable reporters to learn about current events, diversity viewpoints, and connect with authoritative sources. These numerous and intricate ways in which X and Meta's vibrant online communities are used to inform the news cycle highlight the critical role that social media plays in modern news production and call for more research into the specifics of how journalists use, value, or reject social media in their daily work.

The significance of social media applications was buttressed when the Global Investigative Journalism Network (GIJN) and Nepal Investigative Multimedia Journalism Network (NIMJN) used zoom, a virtual video conferencing platform, to organise training for Nepali investigative journalists in August 2020 in attempt to teach journalists how to use social media for investigative purposes. Similarly, to train hundreds of reporters from around the world in social media journalism, 80 of the top investigative journalists in the world came together in Kathmandu, Nepal, from the New York Times, The Guardian, and other reputable publishing outlets. It is thus evident that global and regional networks of investigative journalists, fuelled by globalisation and an explosion in data and communication technology, are growing increasingly in

effectiveness and sophistication. It is against this backdrop that this study investigated the level of awareness of Nigerian investigative journalists on the benefits of social media applications and ascertained the degree of investigative journalists' knowledge of social media applications.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Studies (Abdool, 2015; Tong, 2015; Wang, 2016) in South Africa and China revealed the positive impact of social media technologies on journalism practice as investigative journalists are benefiting from a variety of social media technologies to source, gather, and publish in-depth research reports. While activists, NGOs, environmentalists, and public intellectuals use social media to communicate their opinions and demands, providing information for journalists to conduct investigative reporting, particularly in politically sensitive cases, investigative journalists use social media platforms to gather information from posts and photos, create profiles, look for interesting data, and communicate with other journalists outside of the country.

It thus becomes an area of concern that if investigative journalists in other regions of the world are becoming aware of the benefits of social media applications and are taking initiatives to exploit those applications for improvement, then the core question of whether investigative journalists in Africa, especially Nigeria, are aware of the usefulness of social media platform as a more open, free and participatory platform for gathering essential information in the public domain that could aid investigation must be asked with the intention of ascertaining investigative journalists' extent of knowledge and skill to navigate the platform for sourcing investigative material. Journalists' apathy towards the use of these social media applications or being a laggard of the adoption of social media application tools may have detrimental effect on their access to credible and vast repertoire of information and news sources, while also stalling the deepening of investigative Journalism skills.

It is against this backdrop that this study is conducted in the Southwest region of Nigeria to ascertain investigative journalists' level of awareness of the benefits of social media applications for sourcing investigative data and find out their extent of knowledge of the functions and usages of social media applications for investigative purposes. Hence the study is set to answer the following questions:

1. What are the most commonly used social media applications among investigative journalists in Southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of awareness of investigative journalists on the benefits of social media applications for gathering investigative data in Southwest, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of investigative journalists' knowledge of the functions and usage of social media applications for investigation in Southwest, Nigeria?
4. Do investigative journalists use social media applications for sourcing information in Southwest, Nigeria?

2. CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

2. 1. Investigative Journalist

An investigative journalist is someone who unearths and makes public all pertinent data in order to reveal topics that are hidden, either on purpose by someone in a position of authority or unintentionally, behind a chaotic mass of facts and situations. According to Lanosga, Willnat, Weaver, and Houston (2017), an investigative journalist is someone who thoroughly analyses a single area of interest, such as significant crimes, government corruption, or corporate misconduct. An investigative journalist may put months or even years into their investigation and report-writing. When describing the responsibilities of investigative reporters, media professionals occasionally use the terms "watchdog reporting" or "accountability reporting". On a single story, an investigative journalist may employ one or more of the following resources, in addition to others:

- Document analysis includes examination of court cases, other legal records, tax returns, official reports, regulatory reports, and business financial filings.
- Public record databases.
- Technological investigation, including examination of governmental and commercial practices and their impacts.
- Investigating social and legal problems
- Several on-the-record interviews as well as, occasionally, conversations with anonymous sources (for instance, whistleblowers).
- State or federal Freedom of Information Acts, which enable citizens to request information from public institutions.
- OSINT (Open-Source Intelligence) databases and systems that offer publicly accessible, cost-free resources.

Investigative journalism is viewed as a unique component of the news media industry and even as the profession's mainstay in both traditional and modern debate about journalism (Bjerknes, 2020). Journalists who work in this specialised area of news reporting are portrayed as elite hunters or explorers of significant news stories, whose background inspires feelings of unwavering confidence. In contrast to the perspective or outlook chosen by professionals working in conventional or routine reporting, investigative journalism is typically associated with having a more intrusive, critical, or skeptic mindset (Lanosga et. al, 2017). Thus, investigative journalism can be described as systematic, in-depth and original research and reporting, often involving the unearthing of secrets, heavy use of public records and computer assisted reporting, with a focus on social justice and accountability (Investigative Reporters & Editors, 1983).

2.2 Concept of Social Media Applications (SMAs)

Any web-based application that makes it easier to post and share material (text, video, audio, and photo), create personal profiles, interact with communities, and search for communities is considered a social media application, according to Kaplan (2014). Facebook Messenger (931 million users), Douyin (715 million users), Telegram (700 million users), Instagram (2 billion users), WeChat (1.31 billion users), TikTok (1.05 billion users), YouTube (2.51 billion users), WhatsApp (2 billion users), Instagram (2 billion users), and Snapchat (635 million users) were the most popular social media apps in Nigeria, according to DataReportal (2013).

2.3 Benefits of Social Media Applications to Investigative Journalists

Lavrusik (2010) observed that investigative journalists use social media tools to improve investigative research and reporting through distributed reporting and the creation of an integrated, networked newsroom. According to Australian journalist Gearing (2014), investigative journalists can use social media apps and web-based interactions to work together on global investigations and reach a larger audience. According to Gearing's paper, "Investigative Journalism in a Socially Networked World," by promoting the use of social media and web-based communications for journalistic investigations, a global viewpoint can benefit local, regional, and national stories. In other words, using social media and other communication technologies can help to broaden the scope of investigations and provide a more comprehensive understanding of issues. One of the main arguments made by Gearing (2014) in support of the use of social media applications for investigations was that investigative journalists are a part of a networked society. Social media has made it possible for people from different countries to connect and conduct study on global investigative issues. By using social media platforms, collaborating with other reporters, or establishing partnerships with domestic or foreign media outlets, investigative journalists who apply their analogue reporting techniques to the digital sphere may be able to find or be found by global stories (Gering, 2014). Social media applications are able to lead to collaboration between reporters domestically or across borders that may lead to reporters working together or sharing contacts and this could be powerful in holding people to account.

Having a presence on social media and the internet in general makes investigative journalists more accessible. In addition to their own personal contacts, journalists with websites, blogs, social media pages, and other online presences may get messages from interest groups, contacts of contacts, and other potential news sources (Gering, 2014). This leads to the creation of better possibilities for identifying investigative topics to look into or sources and information. As concluded by Gearing (2014), it seems plausible that online networks might provide investigative journalists in the network society new ways of working that would allow them to cover more stories in greater depth and breadth. Making use of these network connections can result in synergies that facilitate the

reporting of global news, especially sensitive or contentious topics. Investigative journalists working with online networks have the ability to expand the types of stories that can be shared and the number of voices that can be heard by holding the strong accountable and giving voice to the voiceless. Social media platforms can be used by investigative journalists to track down a person or a story, as well as to build profiles of the people they are investigating. The public can learn more about an individual's private activities by looking at their Meta and X pages, which contain details about their family, friends, professional affiliations, likes and dislikes, and even travel history (Nazakat, 2012).

2.4 Social Media and Multimedia Functions

Multimedia, according to Akinreti (2007), is a notion that allows text, audio, images, and graphics to be processed into a single medium for multiple users simultaneously. The ability for people to engage with these elements to their pleasure is what makes multimedia so powerful. A feedback mechanism is guaranteed in order words. Text, pictures, computer software, video images, and audio recordings are only a few of the many digital materials included in these multimedia files (De Maeyer, 2012). This material is available to you online. The term "multimedia" originates from the internet's multifaceted nature. Therefore, the work of collecting, publishing, editing, and sharing information online in the form of text, graphics, images, video, audio, and computer software is known as multimedia journalism.

Stevens (2008) defines a multimedia story as a nonlinear online presentation of text, still images, video, audio, graphics, and interactive elements where the information in each medium is complementary rather than redundant. The term "non-linear" refers to the flexibility to tell a tale without following a set format. To put it another way, a non-linear story may begin with text and then use audio, video, and graphics to explain other sections of the story instead of relying solely on text. In contrast, a linear story told in a single medium, like as text, is supposed to be presented in a straight jacket manner.

There are two ways that multimedia stories might be collected and displayed. A single tale can be presented on a media website as entirely text, entirely video, or entirely audio, as previously mentioned, or it can be woven into many media forms as stated above, giving the reader, listener, or viewer the option to select his preferred view. Multimedia tales fall into two categories: editor or producer driven and the second is reporter driven. Journalist-driven articles are created when a reporter on a beat decides to compile news from his beat in a multimedia style.

However, social media forms part of the much of the Internet and thus far is credited with the highest activity on the internet (Lynne, as cited in Apuke, 2017). The interactivity feature of social media is essentially what attracts such huge activity. It also integrates multimedia capabilities of video, pictures, text, 2D and 3D contents that can be uploaded

and allowing journalists and media organisations to maintain contacts with their audience (Igyuve, Inobemhe, Udeh & Ugber, 2020).

3. THEORETICAL REVIEW

E.M. Rogers, a communication theorist at the University of New Mexico, created the diffusion of innovations hypothesis in 1962. The theory describes how various individuals who engage with or start adopting a new idea go through stages of adoption. The major figures in the theory of dissemination of innovations are:

- Those that take chances and are the first to try new things are known as innovators.
- Those who are eager to test new technologies and determine their value to society are known as early adopters.
- Early majority: People from the general population who open the door for an innovation to be used in mainstream society.
- Late majority: People who follow the early majority into adopting the innovation as part of their daily life and are also part of the general population.
- Laggards: Individuals who adopt new ideas and creative products later than the overall population (Rogers, 1962).

The perceived characteristics of technology and the inventiveness of the organisations implementing them have been the primary focus of the Diffusion of Innovation theory. According to Rogers (2003), there are five characteristics of an innovation that affect its uptake: relative advantage over current technologies, compatibility with organisational workflows and knowledge, trialability, complexity to implement, and observability of the innovation's development both within the organisation and among competitors. The rate at which innovations are adopted is predicted by an individual's perceptions of these five traits.

For the purpose of researching the stages of adoption, Rogers (2003) suggested an innovation-decision process model, which is essentially an information-seeking and information-processing activity in which the person is motivated to lessen uncertainty regarding the benefits and drawbacks of a particular innovation. An individual or other decision-making unit goes through the following steps in the innovation decision process: learning about the innovation, developing an attitude towards it, deciding whether to accept or reject it, putting the new idea into practice, and then having this decision confirmed.

The concept of information exchange throughout social media networks is maintained by social media, a technical advancement. Individuals use a variety of social networking apps for a range of reasons. One group of persons in society who are expected to be tech-savvy and interested in experimenting with new technologies and determining their

applicability to media practice are journalists. They can construct a social media network where information can be produced, disseminated, and sourced. In light of international investigative journalism methods that might encourage investigative inquiry and collaboration, new technical concepts must be adopted for increased competency and professionalism. Investigative journalists in several parts of the world are familiar with the concept of using social media applications for a variety of investigative purposes, and early adopters are reaping significant benefits from it.

4. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Abdenour's 2016 study focused on ascertaining if social media websites help investigative journalists to do their job more effectively with 165 respondents participating in the survey. The study found out that the majority of the local television journalists use social media as part of their daily information gathering exercise. It submitted that though traditional news gathering methods are still alive, the use of social media has become the common practice.

Posetti (2013) investigated the implications of the 'Twitterisation' of investigative Journalism, its benefits for research, investigation and verification with its pitfalls, and how journalists can effectively deploy social media platforms in developing and reporting investigative stories. The study employed grounded theory and qualitative data analysis methods using a combination of online interviews, case study, focus group discussion, and qualitative survey with all focusing on the usage of social media for investigative Journalism with particular attention on Twitter. It found breaking and dissemination of news in real-time, news gathering, audience engagement, information sharing, subversion of spin, journalist-brands marketing, and public engagement with one another as the core functions of Twitter for the journalists. Posetti identified verification problem as the major pitfall of social media as there are lots of incorrect and exaggerated information usually reported without fact checking. He emphasized that journalists must always verify information, upskill, deploy deeper search function for information gathering, and verify an account as 'real' person among others.

Pathak (2018) did an evaluative study of the influence of social media on journalism on whether it an interference or professional advancement. If found out the usage pattern of social media by Indian journalists and their perception about its use by employing a quantitative survey of 150 respondents and found that 96 per cent of the respondents considered social media as a vital tool for professional development while majority of them use it for sharing news, tweeting news, posting images and responding to reader's views.

This study recognizes the various relevant works done on the use of social media by journalists for their professional practices but it is particular on the use of social media for investigative journalism. The scope of this study covers the perception of journalists in Southwest Nigeria.

5. **METHODOLOGY**

Quantitative survey design was adopted for the study. This research design is most suitable for the study because it enabled the researcher to quantify variables and collect numerical data using the instrument of questionnaire. The area of study was Southwest, Nigeria where the highest numbers of print media organisations are concentrated and equally considered as the cradle of journalism in Nigeria. The study population consisted of journalists that belong to the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) in the six geo-political states in Southwest, Nigeria that is NUJ Lagos Corporate Office, Ogun, Oyo, Ondo, Ekiti and Osun States' Chapters with population estimation of 3, 276 (Source: NUJ Chapters' Membership Database (April, 2023)). The study composed its population from these chapters because they have press centres and chapels for practicing journalists. The study got an aggregate sample of 344 using the online sample size calculator with 95% confidence level, 5% margin error and 50% population proportion.

Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the quantitative research. The researcher started using the convenience sampling technique by physically administering copies of the questionnaire to journalists at their monthly congress in each state chapter. Moreso, the researcher adapted the snowball technique by liaising with each chapter to make referral to as many identified investigative journalists in Southwest, Nigeria who are willing to participate in the study. In the end, the purposive sampling technique was employed to select determined number of qualified investigative journalists out of the aggregate sampled population for data analysis.

However, in order to determine who qualified as investigative journalist for the research, the study operationalized that only respondents that indicated to having published any story(ies) that had proof of time and research; stories that had any political importance or significance in the public eye; stories that pointed out victims or perpetrators; stories that looked into a betrayal of the public trust: and stories that sought out a secret truth that is beneficial to society were purposefully selected. Data analysis was done using simple percentage and frequency counts to determine investigative journalists' level of awareness and knowledge of social media applications for investigation in Southwest, Nigeria.

5.1 Results and Presentation

Out of the 344 journalists that filled out the questionnaire only 326 respondents met the criteria for selection as investigative journalists for the study. Descriptive statistics were used for the analysis of the quantitative data.

Table 1: Respondents' demographic Analysis

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	216	66.3%
Female	110	33.7%
Total	326	100%
Educational Status		
OND	41	12.4%
HND	72	22.0%
First Degree	82	25.2%
PGD/Masters	129	40.0%
Ph.D	2	0.4%
Total	326	100%
Work Experience		
5yrs-10 years	201	61.7%
10 years and above	125	38.3%
Total	326	100%

Author's Field Survey, 2023

Table 1 showed greater number of male respondents with 216 (66.3%). The tables showed that majority (40%) of the respondents are postgraduate degree holders. Moreso, greater number (61.7%) of the respondents have been working for 5 to 10 years while 16.3% of the respondents had won one award or the other in different categories in investigative journalism.

Research Question 1: Types of social media applications common among investigative journalists

Table 2: Social Media Commonly Used by Investigative Journalists

Variables	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Total
X	209(64.1%)	70(21.5%)	47(14.4%)	-	326(100%)
Facebook	167(51.2%)	98(30.1%)	61(18.7%)	-	326(100%)
Instagram	84(25.8%)	169(51.8%)	71(21.8%)	2(0.6%)	326(100%)
Tiktok	172(52.8%)	80(24.5%)	65(20%)	9(2.77%)	326(100%)
FB Messenger	82(25.2%)	126(37.0%)	115(35.2%)	3(0.92%)	326(100%)
WhatsApp	212(65.0%)	67(20.6%)	47(14.4%)-	-	326(100%)
Snapchat	87(26.0%)	129(40.0%)	110(34.0%)	-	326(100%)
YouTube	176(54%)	85(26.0%)	63(19.3%)	2(0.61%)	326(100%)
Linkedin	114(35.0%)	116(36.0%)	92(29.0%)	4(1.22%)	326(100%)
Telegram	179(55.0%)	78(24.0%)	69(21.0%)	-	326(100%)

Author's Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 indicated X as the highest common among investigative journalists with 85.6%, followed by WhatsApp (85.6%), Facebook (81.3%), YouTube (80%), Telegram (79%), Instagram (77.6%), TikTok (77.3%) LinkedIn (71%), Snapchat (66.0%), FB Messengar (62.2%).

The analysis implied that investigative journalists use all the social media applications optimally but X, WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube are highest in order of usage. Thus, it could be inferred that investigative journalists use X, WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube more for gathering information.

Research Question 2: What is the level of awareness of investigative journalists on the benefits of social media applications for gathering investigative data in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Level of awareness of Investigative Journalists on the Benefits of Social Media Applications (SMAs) for gathering investigative data

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Mean	SD
SMAs are participatory platforms that allows for user-generated content useful for investigative reporting	163(50%)	149(45.%)	12(3.7%)	2(0.6%)	326	3.30	0.46
SMAs enhance sharing of news contents, comments and photos within one’s own virtual network	112(34.4%)	195(59.%)	19(5.8%)	-	326	3.27	0.44
SMAs allow users to engage with news in variety of ways, including consume news, discover news and share or repost news	201(61.7%)	116(35.%)	4(1.2%)	5(1.5%)	326	3.37	0.48
SMAs allow for exportation of comments, posts. photos and videos. profile search useful for investigation	198(60.7%)	107(32.%)	10(3.1%)	11(3.4%)	326	3.57	0.50
SMAs can be used to obtain local news feeds and create live videos where investigative leads can emanate from	167(51.2%)	151(46.%)	9(2.8%)	-	326	3.27	0.44
SMAs allow Investigative journalists to ask for users’ or experts’ recommendations on topical issues or trends.	132(40.5%)	108(33.%)	65(19.9%)	21(6.4%)	326	3.17	0.38
SMAs allow Investigative Journalists to track, monitor	181(55.5%)	77(23.6%)	40(12.3%)	28(8.6%)	326	3.10	0.30

Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Mean	SD
and analyse events or trends for investigative purposes.							
SMA's are significant in news sourcing and monitoring	198(60.7%)	58(17.8%)	25(7.7%)	45(13.8%)	326	3.34	0.47
SMA's are prominent for firsthand news and real-time information	157(48.2%)	120(36.%)	37(11.3%)	12(3.7%)	326	3.10	0.30
SMA's can provide Investigative journalists useful leads into investigation	170(52.1%)	96(29.4%)	54(16.6%)	6(1.8%)	326	3.24	0.43
SMA's allow Investigative journalists find contact sources and confirm facts	156(47.9%)	103(31.%)	67(20.6%)	-	326	3.56	0.50
SMA's allow Investigative journalists to explore and analyse information for advanced textual insights	204(62.6%)	101(31%)	10(3.1%)	11(3.4%)	326	3.50	0.50
SMA's allow investigative Journalists to crowd source for both for "on-the-ground" information-gathering and document analysis	95(29.1%)	196(60.%)	21(6.4%)	14(4.3%)	326	3.53	0.50
SMA's allow investigative journalists to download videos that can enhance investigative reporting	115(35.3%)	196(60.%)	11(3.4%)	4(1.2%)	326	3.13	0.34

Criteria Mean = 2.50 ; Average Mean = 3.32

Author's Field Survey, 2023

Decision rule: 1-1.9 (Very Low); 2-2.49 (Low); 2.5-3.49 (High), 3.50-4.00 (Very High)

Table 3 presented the descriptive statistics showing level of awareness of investigative journalists on the benefits of Social Media applications for gathering investigative data. Findings above indicated that investigative journalists have a high level of awareness of Social Media applications and the inherent benefits of SMA's for gathering investigative data (Average mean of 3.32 > the Criteria mean of 2.50).

Research Question 3: What is the level of investigative journalists’ knowledge of the functions and usage of SMAs for investigation in Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 4: Level of Investigative Journalists’ knowledge of functions and usage of SMAs

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
High	216	66.3%
Moderate	74	22.7%
Low	36	11.0%
Total	326	100%

Author’s Field Survey, 2023

Table 4 revealed that investigative journalists have high knowledge of functions and usage of social media applications with 89% (High and Moderate). This finding implied that majority of investigative journalists in Southwest, Nigeria are both aware and have good knowledge of how social media applications could be employed to search and obtain information from the public.

Research Question 4: Do investigative journalists in Southwest, Nigeria use social media application for sourcing information?

Table 5: Determinants of Usage of SMAs for sourcing information

Variables	Yes	No	Neutral	Total (%)
Effectiveness of SMAs than existing sources e.g (FOIA)	260(79%)	116(21%)	-	326(100%)
Compatibility with the organization’s knowledge, workflows, and policy	217(67%)	95(29%)	13(4%)	326(100%)
Simplicity to use	246(75%)	36(11%)	44(14%)	326(100%)
Ethical Challenges	260(80%)	49(15%)	17(5%)	326(100%)
Journalists Perceptions of SMAs	189(58%)	102(31%)	35(11%)	326(100%)

Author’s Field Survey, 2023

Table 5 revealed that a high number of investigative journalists (79%) would use SMAs if it would be effective than existing sources. With 67% investigative journalists are ready to use SMAs if their organization is knowledgeable in social media journalism and find it

compatible with their organization workflows and policy. 75% investigative journalists are willing to use SMAs if they consider SMAs simple to use but they opined that the ethical dilemma inherent in social media application for investigation may debar them from using them and that their general perception (89%) of social media may also influence them otherwise.

Table 6: Do Investigative Journalists in Southwest Use SMAs for sourcing information

	Frequency	Percentage
Very well	91	28.0%
Some times	60	18.4%
Rarely	104	32.0%
Not at all	34	10.4%
Neutral	37	11.2%
Total	326	100%

Author's Field Survey, 2023

In table 6, only 28% investigative journalists agreed to making utmost use of social media applications for information sourcing while 18.4% utilize them sometimes. This finding indicated that less than half (46.4%) investigative journalists are well disposed to using social media applications for sourcing information in Southwest, Nigeria. This indicated that the remaining 53.6% may either not be so interested or are neutral to the idea of social media applications usage for investigation based on the determinants responsible for the adoption of SMAs.

5.2 Discussion of Findings

Findings from the quantitative research revealed that investigative journalists are conversant with virtually all the popular social media applications in Nigeria but the study found the social media applications like X, WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube as the most popular amongst investigative journalists. This could be inferred that X, WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube are the most prominent platforms for investigative journalists to gather information. This finding buttressed Didiugwu, Ezugwu and Ekwe (2015) who averred that for journalists and news organizations, social networks, especially twitter (X) and Facebook provide an opportunity for connecting with people, distributing news stories and complementing news coverage with feeds from social media. Furthermore, *YouTube* provides a wide range of information and news channels as a global platform for journalism (Sumiala & Tikka, 2013). *YouTube* has developed into such a remarkable tool for journalists and media organisations in their daily job. Along with offering a variety of news stories, it also recommends videos to viewers based on material they have already viewed.

Moreso, the finding revealed that investigative journalists had a high level of awareness on the use of social media applications for gathering investigative data with an average mean of 3.32 > the Criteria mean of 2.50. The implication of this result is that greater numbers of respondents are aware that investigative journalists can crowd source on social media for on-the-ground information gathering and document analysis. Similarly, Journalists are aware that images, texts, pictures and videos can be downloaded to develop stories. In the same vein, finding implied that majority of investigative journalists in Southwest, Nigeria are both aware and have good knowledge of how social media applications function and they know that they can use SMAs to search and obtain information from the public domain. This finding is consistent with Igyuve, Inobemhe, Udeh and Ugber, 2020 who averred that social media integrates multimedia capabilities. Video, pictures, text, 2D and 3D contents can be uploaded with the help of social media allowing journalists and media organisations to maintain contacts with their audience.

In another finding, the readiness of investigative journalists to adopt social media applications for investigation would be determined by the perceived effectiveness of SMAs compared to other existing sources like the freedom of information act etc. It became evident that majority of investigative journalists would also be ready to use SMAs if their organization is knowledgeable in social media journalism and also find it compatible with their organization's workflow and policy. Similarly, virtually all investigative journalists are willing to use SMAs if they find them simple to use but opined that the ethical dilemma of social media application for investigation and investigative journalists' general perception of social media may influence them otherwise.

Lastly, findings indicated that less than average of investigative journalists are using social media applications for sourcing information in Southwest, Nigeria. This finding established the fact that even though majority of investigative journalists interacted and engaged with mass audience on their commonly used platforms, (X, WhatsApp, Facebook and YouTube), and they are very much aware of how these social media applications could be beneficial in terms of connecting people and sourcing materials that could facilitate writing of investigative story, yet most investigative journalists did not use SMAs for that purpose. Non usage of SMAs by investigative journalists may be connected to the previous findings which revealed that investigative journalists may not use SMAs if they find it less effective for investigative purposes; if their organization is less knowledgeable in social media journalism and also find the practice incompatible with their organization's workflow and policy. Moreso, if the ethical challenge in social media application for investigation is high, they may be discouraged from its usage. Outcome of this study infers that social media applications for investigation may have less significant influence on investigative journalism. The outcome of this study is the opposite of previous studies (Abdool, 2015; Tong , 2015 & Wang , 2016) in South Africa and China that revealed the

positive impact of social media applications on journalism practice where investigative journalists are benefiting from a variety of social media applications to source, gather, and publish in-depth research reports. In conjunction with the assumption of diffusion of innovation theory, the outcome of this study confirmed that investigative journalists in Nigeria lag behind in the adoption social media innovation for the improvement of investigative journalism.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study showed positive indications that social media applications are ubiquitous with investigative journalists but SMAs are not increasingly relevant for investigation. According to the study, the awareness of SMAs as information avenues does not yet prompt investigative journalists to utilize them to improve investigative practices. As a result, investigative journalists' ability to gain full understanding of the potentials of social media for undertaking journalistic investigations that can lead to the adoption of a global perspective, enriching local, regional and national stories is undermined. Hence, this study recommends that media organisations should encourage journalists in the act of social media investigative journalism and provide facilities that could help them perform efficiently in this area. Media organizations should gain perspective into the needs for training their investigative journalists for skill to use social media tools for investigative purposes. Investigative Journalists should be devoted to the exploration of social media technology and engage better in the use of the diverse SMAs for investigative purposes, and that media organizations and journalists should device means to harness and integrate the new digital sourcing trend as an alternative or supplementary to the traditional data gathering system.

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